

Influence of Aggregate Size on Core Microbial Communities and Functional Group Selection in Full-Scale Aerobic Granular Sludge Systems

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Abstract

Aerobic granular sludge (AGS) technology is gaining attention as an effective solution for biological wastewater treatment due to its low energy consumption, compact design, and efficient nutrient removal. AGS systems consist of microbial aggregates of various sizes, with granules making up 80%, each supporting distinct microbial communities. However, it remains unclear whether full-scale AGS WWTPs select core microbial communities across different aggregate sizes and how these communities differ. This study addresses this gap by analyzing samples from nine high-performing AGS WWTPs. The results reveal that site-specific conditions influence microbial composition in smaller aggregates, while larger granules form stable, site-independent communities. Despite this, all aggregates shared 128–139 core operational taxonomic units, including key functional groups involved in organics and nutrient removal. Enrichment patterns showed aerobic heterotrophs in flocs, polyphosphate-accumulating organisms in small granules, and glycogen-accumulating organisms and nitrifiers in large granules.

Keywords

Aerobic granular sludge; Core community; Microbial aggregates; Wastewater treatment

INTRODUCTION

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are essential for removing pollutants, safeguarding the environment, and protecting public health (Ruiz-Haddad et al., 2024). Aerobic granular sludge (AGS) technology holds great promise to become the standard for biological wastewater treatment due to its low energy consumption, small footprint, and high removal efficiency of nutrients compared to the conventional activated sludge (AS) process (Ali et al., 2019). AGS systems form microbial aggregates of varying sizes, including flocs and granules, with granules making up 80% (Ekholm et al., 2022; Pronk et al., 2015). Studies have shown that aggregate size significantly influences the selective pressures on microbial communities, with larger aggregates benefiting from improved settling, longer solids retention times, increased substrate availability, and gradients that support diverse niches and microbial specialization (Dueholm et al., 2022; Ali et al., 2019; Winkler et al., 2018). Consequently, it is hypothesized that each aggregate size hosts a distinct core microbial community contributing to aggregate and WWTP stability. However, previous studies, mostly focused on a limited number of full-scale AGS WWTPs, have primarily examined species sorting, community comparisons with AS systems, or omic approaches, leaving this hypothesis untested across multiple full-scale AGS WWTP (Ali et al., 2019; Ekholm et al., 2022; Kleikamp et al., 2023). To address these gaps, this study identifies core microbial communities in each aggregate size from nine full-scale AGS WWTPs, offering insights for developing size-specific strategies to enhance treatment efficiency and predict system stability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples from full-scale AGS WWTPs

Samples were collected from nine Nereda® AGS WWTPs in five European countries, selected for their high performance in carbon and nutrient removal. The WWTPs consistently

achieved average removal rates of 96% for biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), 95% for chemical oxygen demand (COD), 96% for nitrogen, and 86% for phosphorus, ensuring effective nutrient removal and stable operation for two years. Then, triplicate samples (400 mL) of influent and mixed liquor were collected from each WWTP 1 meter below the surface, 30 min after aeration, to ensure uniform mixing. The mixed liquor samples were sieved through cell strainers to obtain triplicate samples for flocs (<0.2 mm), small granules (0.2–0.5 mm), medium granules (0.5–1 mm), and large granules (>1 mm). Mixed liquor composition was primarily composed of large granules (65%), followed by small and medium granules (22%) and flocs (13%). Samples were stored at –80°C for DNA extraction.

DNA Extraction, sequencing, and bioinformatic processing

DNA extraction was performed using a modified FastDNA protocol, followed by preparation of amplicon libraries targeting bacterial 16S rRNA gene regions V1–V8 using a custom protocol. Sequencing was conducted on the Oxford Nanopore MinION platform. Sequencing reads were filtered for length (320–2000 bp) and quality (phred score > 15) using filtlong v0.2.1. The filtered reads were mapped to the SILVA 138.1 99% NR database using minimap2 v2.24 (Li, 2018), followed by processing with samtools v1.14 (Danecek et al., 2021).

Microbial community analyses

Taxonomic beta-diversity between samples were calculated using the Bray–Curtis metric with the `vegdist` function from the `vegan` R package version 2.6–4 (Oksanen et al., 2022). These distances were visualized using principal component analysis (PCA) with the `ampvis2.1` R package (Andersen et al., 2018). Core operational taxonomic units (OTUs) and core genera were determined as taxa present with relative abundance > 0.1% and detected in over 80% of the nine sampled WWTPs using the `ampvis2` package (Andersen et al., 2018). Network-based analysis and visualization were performed with open-source software Cytoscape v.3.5.148. Enrichment analysis was conducted using relative abundance data from the `ampvis2.1` R package and visualized with the `ggplot2` R package.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our analysis revealed that while each WWTP hosts high site-specific diversity, geographically closer WWTPs did not cluster together (Figure 1A). However, aggregate size patterns clustered more closely when influent wastewater was similar, highlighting the role of microbial immigration (Figure 1B). Smaller aggregates (<1 mm) clustered by WWTP, while larger granules exhibited more homogeneous communities across WWTPs (Figure 1C), suggesting that smaller aggregates are more influenced by site-specific conditions. Additionally, all aggregate sizes contained a high density of low-abundance OTUs and a small subset of abundant, prevalent OTUs (core) (Figure 1D). These findings imply that stochastic processes primarily drive low-abundance OTUs, while core OTUs are selectively maintained for their functional significance in AGS system performance. Most core OTUs were consistently shared across aggregate sizes and included key functional groups essential for WWTP performance, such as fermenters, aerobic heterotrophs, polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (PAOs), glycogen-accumulating organisms (GAOs), and nitrifiers (Figure 2). This pattern indicates robust selection of these functional groups, regardless of aggregate size. Despite the conserved presence of core functional groups, variations in their enrichment patterns were observed based on aggregate size. This suggests that, while the AGS system exerts strong selective pressures, aggregate size significantly influences the distribution and dominance of these functional guilds. For example, aerobic heterotrophs dominated in flocs, PAOs in small granules, and GAOs and nitrifiers in large granules (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Microbial Community PCA and Shared OTUs: A) WWTPs, B) WWTPs with influent WW, and C) Sample types (flocs, small granules). IRL stands for Ireland, NIR for Northern Ireland, SCO for Scotland, ENG for England, and NL for the Netherlands. D) OTU distribution by sample type in solid lines and relative abundances in dashed lines, showing values for OTUs exclusive to individual WWTPs, shared among 2-8 WWTPs, and common across all nine plants.

Figure 2. Microbial co-occurrence analysis of core genera across aggregate sizes. Nodes represent genera and are color-coded by their reported functions. The node size reflects the degree of uniqueness of genera to specific aggregate sizes, with the largest node size

indicating genera common across all aggregate sizes. Edge colors denote the source of the genera: flocs (FL), small granules (SG), medium granules (MG), and large granules (LG). Additionally, the Venn diagram summarizes the shared genera among the four aggregate sizes observed in the genera-network analysis. The numbers in brackets represent the number of classified core genera in each aggregate size.

Figure 3. Functional microbial composition across the different-sized aggregates. A-D). Graphs depicting the relative abundances of the functional groups across the different-sized aggregates: A) PAOs, B) GAOs, C) nitrite oxidizing bacteria (NOB), and D) ammonia oxidizing bacteria (AOB). Each graph features two columns representing the analyzed groups: Total (gray), which encompasses all functional genera (i.e., both core and non-core), and Core (light blue), which shows the relative abundances of functional genera found exclusively in the core.

REFERENCES

- Ali, M., Wang, Z., Salam, K.W., Hari, A.R., Pronk, M., Van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Saikaly, P.E., 2019. Importance of species sorting and immigration on the bacterial assembly of different-sized aggregates in a full-scale aerobic granular sludge plant. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53, 8291–8301. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b07303>
- Andersen, K.S., Kirkegaard, R.H., Karst, S.M., Albertsen, M., 2018. ampvis2: an R package to analyse and visualise 16S rRNA amplicon data (preprint). *Bioinformatics*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/299537>
- Danecek, P., Bonfield, J.K., Liddle, J., Marshall, J., Ohan, V., Pollard, M.O., Whitwham, A., Keane, T., McCarthy, S.A., Davies, R.M., Li, H., 2021. Twelve years of SAMtools and BCFtools. *GigaScience* 10, giab008. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giab008>
- Dueholm, M.K.D., Nierychlo, M., Andersen, K.S., Rudkjøbing, V., Knutsson, S., MiDAS Global Consortium, Arriaga, S., Bakke, R., Boon, N., Bux, F., Christensson, M., Chua, A.S.M., Curtis, T.P., Cytryn, E., Erijman, L., Etchebehere, C., Fatta-Kassinos, D., Frigon, D., Garcia-Chaves, M.C., Gu, A.Z., Horn, H., Jenkins, D., Kreuzinger, N., Kumari, S., Lanham, A., Law, Y., Leiknes, T., Morgenroth, E., Muszyński, A., Petrovski, S., Pijuan, M., Pillai, S.B., Reis, M.A.M., Rong, Q., Rossetti, S., Seviour, R., Tooker, N., Vainio, P., Van Loosdrecht, M., Vikraman, R., Wanner, J., Weissbrodt, D., Wen, X., Zhang, T., Nielsen, Per H., Albertsen, M., Nielsen, Per Halkjær, 2022. MiDAS 4: A Global Catalogue of Full-Length 16S rRNA Gene Sequences and Taxonomy for Studies of Bacterial Communities in Wastewater Treatment Plants. *Nat Commun* 13, 1908. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29438-7>
- Ekholm, J., Persson, F., De Blois, M., Modin, O., Pronk, M., Van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Suarez, C., Gustavsson, D.J.I., Wilén, B.-M., 2022. Full-scale aerobic granular sludge for municipal wastewater treatment – granule formation, microbial succession, and process performance. *Environ. Sci.: Water Res. Technol.* 8, 3138–3154. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2EW00653G>
- Kleikamp, H.B.C., Grouzdev, D., Schaasberg, P., Van Valderen, R., Van Der Zwaan, R., Wijgaart, R.V.D., Lin, Y., Abbas, B., Pronk, M., Van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Pabst, M., 2023. Metaproteomics, metagenomics and 16S rRNA sequencing provide different perspectives on the aerobic granular sludge microbiome. *Water Research* 246, 120700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120700>
- Li, H., 2018. Minimap2: pairwise alignment for nucleotide sequences. *Bioinformatics* 34, 3094–3100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty191>
- Oksanen, J., Simpson, G.L., Guillaume, B., F., Kindt, R., Legendre, Pierre, Minchin, Peter R., O'Hara, R.B., Solymos, P., Stevens, Szoecs, E, Wagner, H, Barbour, M, Bedward, M, Bolker, B, Borcard, D, Carvalho, G, Chirico, M, De-Caceres, M., Durand, S., Evangelista, H., 2022. vegan: community ecology package.
- Pronk, M., De Kreuk, M.K., De Bruin, B., Kamminga, P., Kleerebezem, R., Van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., 2015. Full scale performance of the aerobic granular sludge process for sewage treatment. *Water Research* 84, 207–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2015.07.011>
- Ruiz-Haddad, L., Ali, M., Pronk, M., Van Loosdrecht, M.C.M., Saikaly, P.E., 2024. Demystifying polyphosphate-accumulating organisms relevant to wastewater treatment: A review of their phylogeny, metabolism, and detection. *Environmental Science and Ecotechnology* 100387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ese.2024.100387>
- Winkler, M.-K.H., Meunier, C., Henriot, O., Mahillon, J., Suárez-Ojeda, M.E., Del Moro, G., De Sanctis, M., Di Iaconi, C., Weissbrodt, D.G., 2018. An integrative review of granular sludge for the biological removal of nutrients and recalcitrant organic matter from wastewater. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 336, 489–502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.12.026>